

THE EFFECTS OF INTERFACIAL DEBONDING AND WORK HARDENING ON THE FRACTURE OF METAL-CERAMIC LAMINATES

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SUMMARY: Experiments are described in which laminates made up of alternate layers of aluminium and alumina have been fractured in bending, with the fracture energy being measured. The testing geometry was such as to ensure that failure occurred by propagation of a single, dominant crack. The effect of debonding has been investigated by systematically reducing the interfacial bond strength. In order to study the deformation and fracture of metal ligaments which bridge cracks in neighbouring ceramic layers, sandwich specimens were tested in tension. A model has been developed in which the contribution from metal ligament deformation has been quantified by adaptation of the Bridgman treatment of constrained notch growth. Application of the model to the commercial purity aluminium used in this work necessitated incorporation of the effect of work hardening. Work hardening raises the work of fracture. Fairly good agreement was observed between prediction and experiment for the work done when a single constrained metal layer was tested in tension. Good agreement was also found when the model was applied to fracture of multi-layered laminates. It is expected that interfacial debonding will raise the fracture energy of a laminate during dominant crack propagation and this was observed experimentally. However, in practice multiple cracking may occur in metal-ceramic laminates. This can raise the fracture energy dramatically, but it also makes it more difficult to predict and likely to be sensitive to the specimen dimensions and loading geometry. Interfacial debonding will tend to reduce the incidence of multiple cracking and hence to reduce the fracture energy in cases where it is likely to occur.

KEYWORDS: metal-ceramic laminates, energy absorption, crack bridging, plastic zone, slip line field, interfacial debonding, crack opening displacement, necking, work hardening

INTRODUCTION

There has been extensive interest [1-8] recently in metal/ceramic laminated materials, which offer the potential for attractive combinations of stiffness, creep resistance, wear properties, strength and toughness. This interest follows earlier work on how ceramics can be toughened by the incorporation of dispersed metallic constituents [9-12]. The key issue for the development of such layered materials concerns the retention of acceptable toughness levels when the laminates have sufficiently high loading of ceramic to confer good stiffness, creep resistance and tribological properties.

There have been several studies [1, 6, 7, 13, 14] aimed at prediction of the fracture energy of a laminate composed of alternate layers of brittle and ductile materials. Such modelling is based on the propagation of a single dominant crack (oriented normal to the plane of the layers), although it is recognised that in practice multiple cracking may occur - particularly with relatively high metal contents [8]. Most of the energy absorbed when such crack propagation takes place is expended in plastic deformation of the metal layers while they bridge the cracks between adjacent ceramic layers. A key issue concerns the effect of the constraint imposed by the surrounding ceramic layers. This constraint tends to raise the initial traction needed to generate plastic flow of the metal. However, it will also tend to limit the plastic strain at failure. The net effect is in general to reduce the work of fracture. It has been recognised [9] for some time that one consequence of this is that the fracture energy is expected to fall (approximately linearly) with decreasing metal layer thickness (for a given overall metal volume fraction), although there has been little experimental validation of this.

In the present study, experimental data are presented from specimens with a strong interfacial bond and also from specimens in which this bond has been deliberately weakened. In modelling the fracture process, particular attention is directed towards the effect of the shape of the bridging ligament, which is affected by interfacial debonding.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Material and Specimen Production

Laminates were prepared by diffusion bonding[6] . The process involves stacking alternate layers of alumina and (commercial purity) aluminium in a vacuum hot press. Pressing was carried out at ~650°C and 4 MPa, for about 4 hours. This procedure generates interfaces which are well bonded. Three different metal layer thicknesses were used, with the same ceramic layer thickness (0.5 mm), so that 3 metal volume fractions (from 8% to 61%) were studied. Each specimen contained 7 ceramic layers. Specimens for bend testing were chevron-notched [8] prior to testing, in order to constrain fracture to a single well defined plane and avoid complications due to multiple cracking. Sandwich specimens were also produced, composed of outer ceramic layers (2 mm thick) and a central metal layer (2.6 mm thick). These were tested in tension, after notching of the two ceramic layers, in order to study the deformation and rupture of a bridging ligament. Specimens were also produced with interfaces which had been weakened in a controlled manner. This was done by spraying a discontinuous graphitic layer onto the interface prior to the bonding process. The area coverage with graphitic material (which inhibited interfacial bonding) was about 50%.

Mechanical Testing

All testing was carried out at room temperature, using a servo-hydraulic machine under displacement control. Specimens were loaded in four-point bending with a roller displacement rate of 0.2 mm min⁻¹. The distance between the inner and the outer rollers varied from 12.5 to 20 mm. Roller displacement was measured using an LVDT. Tensile testing was carried out with a range of strain rates. For the sandwich specimens, a clip gauge was used to measure the changing crack opening displacement as straining continued.

MODELLING OF FRACTURE

The principal contribution to the absorption of energy during cracking by a laminate reinforced by ductile layers has been previously identified as deformation of constrained metal ligaments behind the crack tip [13]. This deformation process can be divided into three distinct regimes: (a) small scale yielding, (b) onset of global yielding and (c) necking of the metal ligament until it ruptures. These are considered in detail below. Elastic properties of the metal and ceramic used in the modelling work, taken to represent aluminium and alumina, were values for E of 70 and 350 GPa and for ν of 0.33 and 0.24 respectively. The metal yield stress, σ_Y , was taken as constant.

Small Scale Yielding

The small scale yielding (SSY) behaviour of a metal near the high stress region of a crack tip has been analysed by several researchers[15, 16] . A relationship between the nominal stress, σ_n , and the opening displacement of the crack, u , has been proposed[7, 17, 18] , based on elementary fracture mechanics under plane strain conditions where σ_Y is the uniaxial yield stress of the metal, E is its Young's modulus, h_m is its thickness and Y is a dimensionless constant.

$$\frac{\sigma_n}{\sigma_Y} \approx Y \sqrt{\frac{\pi E}{2\sigma_Y}} \sqrt{\frac{2u}{h_m}} \quad (1)$$

In order to validate this expression and evaluate Y , finite element (FEM) analysis of the constrained notch problem has been performed, using ABAQUS software[7] . A mesh was set up consisting of an elastic - perfectly plastic (metal) layer between two radially notched elastic (ceramic) layers of equal thickness. This was loaded in tension by uniform displacement of the top surface. The results suggest that Y is not a strong function of the ceramic elastic properties or thickness, but is related to the Poisson ratio of the metal layer. For materials with Poisson ratios lower than 0.4, Y was found to be well approximated by the following expression.

$$Y \approx 0.46 / \sqrt{1-2\nu} \quad (2)$$

The FEM results are shown in Fig. 1 for three different ratios of the initial notch opening, u_0 , to the metal layer thickness, h_m . It is clear that the SSY curve for an initial notch opening of zero, ie an infinitely sharp crack, will be similar in form to those predicted for finite initial openings, albeit with a higher maximum constraint expected at the onset of net section plasticity. The good agreement exhibited over the initial sections of the plots indicates that Eqn.(1) gives a reliable indication of the SSY behaviour. The problem of predicting the maximum constraint (peak value of σ_n / σ_Y) is addressed in the next section.

Fig. 1: Plots of normalised nominal stress against normalised crack opening displacement, as obtained by using Eqn. 1) with the value of Y given by Eqn. 2, and by using FEM analysis. These plots refer to the straining of a single metal layer bonded between two ceramic layers, which have missing sections which constitute the initial crack opening displacement.

Onset and Development of Global Yielding

It is well established that the constraint of plastic yielding in an elastic/ductile composite, as indicated by the ratio of the mean axial stress required for net section yielding to the uniaxial (unconstrained) yield stress, can be large. Values between 3 and 8 have been reported in the literature for layered systems, using either experimental[11, 12] or theoretical[13] approaches. In order to predict the stress field ahead of the notch after the onset of global yielding, and therefore the constraint factor, the present work has involved derivation of slip line field solutions for various geometries, following the procedures of Hill[19], Rice and Johnson[20] and Evans and McMeeking[21]. Three different notch shapes, with square, radial or circular geometries (see Fig. 3) were examined in the current study. Predictions from the slip line field analysis of the case of a radial notch were found to be in very good agreement with an expression derived by Bridgman[22], which gives the distribution of axial stress across the section of the neck, σ_{yy} , as a function of the curvature of the free surface, κ_s , ($=1/R$, where R is the radius of curvature) at the section of minimum area. Modifying Bridgman's original expression so that it is applicable to plane strain, rather than the case of axial symmetry which he treated, leads to the following equation.

$$\frac{\sigma_{yy}}{\sigma_Y} = 1 + \int_x^a \kappa dx \quad (3)$$

where a is the semi-thickness of the metal layer at the minimum section, x is the distance from the centre of the metal layer and κ is the radius of curvature of the principal tensile stress trajectory as it passes through the minimum section of the neck (see Fig. 2). It is clear from Fig. 2 that κ is zero at the centre line ($x = 0$) and rises monotonically to a value of κ_s at the free surface ($x = a$), since there can be no stress acting normally to a free surface. Bridgman proposed the following expression for the variation of κ with x :

$$\kappa = \frac{2x}{a^2 + 2aR - x^2} \quad (4)$$

Fig. 2: Schematic depiction of a section through half of the metal layer during necking, showing the dimensions which characterise the radial notch.

Evaluating the integral in Eqn. 3, after substituting from Eqn. 4, gives:

$$\frac{\sigma_{yy}}{\sigma_Y} = 1 + \ln \left(\frac{a^2 + 2aR - x^2}{2aR} \right) \quad (5)$$

The constraint factor, in terms of the nominal stress, is now found by integrating this stress across the section of the narrowest part of the neck and normalising by the original metal layer thickness, h_m , to give

$$\frac{\sigma_n}{\sigma_Y} = \frac{2}{h_m} \left(2\sqrt{a(2R+a)} \tanh^{-1} \left(\sqrt{\frac{a}{2R+a}} \right) - a \right) \quad (6a)$$

It can be seen from Fig. 2 that $a = (h_m - u)/2$ and $R = u/2$, so that this expression can be rewritten:

$$\frac{\sigma_n}{\sigma_Y} = \left(\frac{\chi}{2} - 1 \right) + 2\sqrt{\left(1 - \frac{\chi^2}{4} \right)} \tanh^{-1} \sqrt{\frac{2-\chi}{2+\chi}} \quad (6b)$$

where the parameter χ represents the normalised crack opening displacement ($\chi = 2u / h_m$). The slip line field predictions for a radial type notch are shown in Fig. 3, together with that from the Bridgman model, represented by Eqn. 6. These two curves are in good agreement, which may be taken as confirmation of the accuracy of the Bridgman formula.

Fig. 3: (a) Predicted plots of the dependence of the nominal stress on the crack opening displacement, obtained from the slip line field treatment and from two versions of the Bridgman equation. (b) Schematic depiction of possible notch geometries

There is, however, a problem with both of these approaches, in that neither takes account of the changes in the shape of the neck which will occur as plastic straining becomes extensive. A basic problem with representing the progression of necking by simply allowing a notch of circular section to progressively increase in radius is that the volume of metal is not conserved during such a process: the simple relationship generated between κ_s and the opening displacement, u , is not physically admissible. A modified form of the Bridgman equation (Eqn. 6) has therefore been developed, based on a conservation of volume approach proposed elsewhere[23] for ductile reinforcements with spherical shape. The resultant modified form of the Bridgman equation is given below.

$$\frac{\sigma_n}{\sigma_Y} = \left(\sqrt{\frac{\chi}{2\pi}} - 1 \right) + \sqrt{\left(4 - \frac{2\chi}{\pi} \right)} \tanh^{-1} \sqrt{\frac{\sqrt{2\pi} - \sqrt{\chi}}{\sqrt{2\pi} + \sqrt{\chi}}} \quad (7)$$

Details of the derivation of this equation are presented elsewhere [24]. The curve predicted using this equation is shown in Fig. 3. It can be seen that the effect of the modification is to reduce the constraint factor immediately after the peak stress, but also to lower the rate at which the nominal stress falls as the crack opening becomes large. This is due to the quadratic relationship found between κ_s and the opening displacement, u , where the notch is initially required to grow very quickly to conserve volume, but after it becomes large it can grow much more slowly.

The Rupture Criterion

Having predicted the behaviour in the initial SSY regime, the maximum constraint factor and the changing load borne by the neck as it thins down, it only remains to identify a criterion for the displacement at which final rupture will occur. This will in practice vary with the fracture characteristics of the metal. In some cases, cavitation and rupture could occur at relatively low displacements, giving a sharp fall in nominal stress as fracture occurs. However, with

highly ductile metals there will be a tendency for the section to progressively neck down to a point, so that after failure the two sections will have included angles of about 90° . This is certainly the type of behaviour observed with the (commercial purity) aluminium used in the present work. Such necking is expected to lead to a progressive reduction in nominal stress, falling to zero at a normalised displacement ($\chi = 2 u / h_m$) of 2.0 (assuming the initial opening is not larger than the metal layer thickness).

It follows that the modified Bridgman curve in Fig. 3 is actually rather unsatisfactory, since it predicts a normalised displacement at rupture which is considerably above $\chi = 2$. It is difficult to derive an analytical expression which takes account of the complex changes in sectional shape which occur as a bridging ligament necks down. However, it is believed that the modified Bridgman equation is reasonably accurate over the initial part of the displacement range, where the notch is still expected to be approximately radial, and only becomes unreliable at large opening displacements, after the radial notch shape has been substantially deformed.

Fig. 4. (a) Predicted plots of the dependence of the nominal stress on the crack opening displacement, showing the effect of the tangent correction (for linear necking) to the modified Bridgman curve. (b) Schematic depiction of initial and final notch geometries .

As a plausible, but arbitrary, attempt to model the very large opening behaviour, a linear dependence of nominal stress on displacement is proposed, by constructing a tangent from the point ($\chi = 2.0, \sigma_n / \sigma_Y = 0$) to the modified Bridgman curve. The full plot is then assumed to follow Eqn. 7 up to this tangent contact point and the tangent itself from there until failure. This is shown graphically in Fig. 4. The initial (SSY) part of the plot is taken as that predicted by FEM; the main point to note about this part of the plot, however, is that the area under the curve (giving the fracture energy) will be very insensitive to the details of the SSY regime, in which an assumption that the stress rises instantly to the maximum constraint factor value would be a perfectly acceptable approximation.

Fracture Energy Prediction

Plots of nominal stress against displacement can be used to obtain the energy absorbed during deformation of the metal ligament, which is given by the area under the curve. The net fracture energy can be obtained from this by adding the contribution from fracture of the

ceramic layers and weighting for the volume fractions of the two constituents. Expressed in terms of normalised displacement and nominal stress, the fracture energy can thus be expressed as

$$G_{tot} = (1 - f_m)G_c + f_m \sigma_Y \frac{h_m}{2} w \quad \text{where } w = \int_0^{\chi_{max}} \frac{\sigma_n}{\sigma_Y} d\chi \quad (8)$$

where χ_{max} is the normalised crack opening displacement when the ligament fractures. The integral, w , can be evaluated once the form of the σ_n/σ_Y against χ plot has been finalised. For example, for the modified Bridgman plot in Fig. 4, with the tangent correction for linear necking, w has a value of 1.61. Providing the values of G_c and σ_Y are known, this would allow the fracture energy to be predicted as a function of the metal volume fraction f_m . It may be noted that, assuming the total energy to be dominated by the contribution from deformation of the metal ligaments (which is normally the case), the fracture energy will increase linearly with h_m , ie with the scale of the layer structure, if the volume fraction of the ductile constituent is held constant. It should, however, be noted that this treatment is based on the assumption that a single crack propagates through the laminate; multiple cracking will raise the value substantially and may occur to different degrees with different scales of layer thickness.

Effect of Work Hardening

Before making a comparison between predicted and measured fracture energies, it should be noted that it has been implicitly assumed hitherto that the yield stress of the metal is a constant and that no work hardening occurs. This assumption needs to be examined carefully, since the plastic strains experienced within the neck region will often become relatively large. Fig. 5 shows an experimental stress-strain plot obtained from tensile testing of a thick sheet of aluminium with a similar composition and microstructure to that of the layers within the laminates. The test was carried out at a strain rate of about $1.4 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

Fig. 5: Stress-strain plots for tensile testing of aluminium with a similar microstructure to that of the layers in the laminates, showing the experimental data and the curve obtained using the equation described in the inset.

It can be seen that the flow stress changes considerably with strain. (This will often be the case with a soft metal, such as unalloyed aluminium which has been annealed.) With such yielding behaviour, it seems likely that significant errors will be introduced by the ascribing of a constant flow stress and it is certainly unclear what single value would be most appropriate in this case. The experimental flow stress is well fitted in the present case by a power law hardening curve having a strain exponent of 0.518 and a yield stress at 1 % strain of 12.2 MPa. The curve was only fitted for stress-strain data above 15 MPa, the point at which yielding started, and before a strain of 51.4 % was attained, when plastic instability occurred. (This is consistent with Considère's construction [25], which predicts the strain at plastic instability to be equal to the strain exponent (=51.8 %).)

The preceding theoretical treatment may be assumed to apply for the case of σ_Y being a function of plastic strain. The predicted area under the plot of normalised nominal stress against normalised displacement will be unaffected. There is, however, a difficulty in attributing a value to the σ_Y term outside the integral in Eqn. 8. If it is assumed that the longitudinal strain across the minimum section is approximately uniform (as Bridgman did), then the most obvious solution is to select a value of σ_Y which represents a weighted average over the range of strain experienced by metal in the ligaments. It should be possible to obtain a reasonable estimate for this in particular cases, perhaps after studying the morphology of failed ligaments.

In order to explore the reliability of using this approach to simulation of the effect of work hardening, tensile tests were conducted on aluminium layers ($h_m = 2.6$ mm) bonded on each side to thick ceramic layers, each being notched through to the metal. The notch width (ie initial crack opening displacement, u_0) was 0.2 mm (so that $\chi_0 = 0.15$). The crack opening displacement during loading was measured with a clip gauge. A typical normalised load-displacement plot is shown in Fig. 6. Normalisation of the load data was carried out using the yield stress / strain dependency from Fig. 5, expressed algebraically in the inset, where the minimum yield stress was taken to be 15 MPa, the value of σ_Y is in MPa and the strain taken to be equal to the increase in notch displacement divided by the original displacement. This relationship between displacement and strain will clearly be unreliable for very small initial displacements, since it effectively assumes that straining is confined to the region within the initial notch, but it should be acceptable for relatively large initial displacements.

The area under the curve in Fig. 6 is about 4.4, which may be compared with the value of w of 1.6 from the modified Bridgman model. Considering the approximations involved in this treatment of work hardening, this represents fair agreement and may be taken as broadly supporting the validity of the modified Bridgman model with the linear necking correction. The major discrepancy between the curves concerns the height of the peak constraint factor. In fact, the magnitude of this peak for the experimental curve is very sensitive to the exact shape of the early part of the flow stress curve and cannot be taken as being reliable. In particular, in this regime the linear relation assumed between strain and notch opening is suspect. In practice, the local strain increased more rapidly with displacement in the early regime than at higher displacements. It follows that the yield stress employed when normalising was too low at small displacements, which has resulted in the normalised nominal stress being too high in this regime. This is an area requiring further investigation.

LAMINATE FRACTURE

Load/displacement plots are shown in Fig. 7 from four-point bending experiments on chevron-notched laminates containing 8%, 35% and 61% of metal by volume. Also shown, for the two higher metal contents, are corresponding plots for laminates with weakened interfaces. The areas under these curves were divided by the corresponding sectional areas to give the fracture energy. Two features are immediately apparent from these plots. Firstly, the fracture energy rises sharply with increasing metal content. This is entirely as expected and it follows from the forms of Eqns. 7 and 8. The second point is that introduction of the weakened interfaces has increased the fracture energy slightly. This is apparently a consequence of an increase in roller displacement at final failure, which presumably arose because interfacial debonding allowed deformation of the metal ligaments to occur over greater lengths. This is consistent with observations made on failed specimens.

The fracture energy data are summarised in Fig. 8, where experimental and predicted values are plotted against the volume fraction of metal. The predicted curves were obtained by substituting the predicted value of the integral w ($= 1.6$) into Eqn. 8 and using three values for the effective yield stress over the strain range, $\bar{\sigma}_Y$: 15, 30 and 60 MPa. These values of the effective yield stress represent the stress at initial yielding of the aluminium, an approximate unweighted average over the strain range observed in Fig. 5 and an intermediate value representing the effect of weighting the effective yield stress towards the lower strain values via the predicted $\sigma_n/\sigma_Y : \chi$ curve (Fig. 4). Clearly, the effect of work hardening in raising the fracture energy is manifest as an increase in the appropriate value of this effective yield stress. The predicted fracture energy is more sensitive to f_m than Eqn. 8 apparently indicates, because it is the ceramic layer thickness, rather than the metal layer thickness, which is being held constant (at a value of 0.5 mm). For this particular case, the curves correspond to the expression:

$$G_{tot} = 20 (1 - f_m) + 402.5 \bar{\sigma}_Y \left(\frac{f_m^2}{1 - f_m} \right) \quad (9)$$

where $\bar{\sigma}_Y$ is the effective yield stress in MPa and the value of 20 J m^{-2} for the fracture energy of alumina has been taken from the literature. In general, the values obtained with the strong interfaces are in quite good agreement with predictions. The experimental values are somewhat higher than those predicted, but this is probably associated with the (limited amount of) local multiple cracking which tends to occur, even with the chevron notch present to constrain the crack plane. (In the absence of the chevron notch, extensive multiple cracking is observed with the higher metal contents [7], which raises the fracture energy substantially.)

Fig. 6: Experimental data for the nominal stress as a function of crack opening displacement for an aluminium layer sandwiched between two pre-notched alumina layers. The stress values have been normalised by the yield stress, which is also shown as a function of crack opening (derived from Fig. 5). The strain was taken as the increase in displacement divided by the original notch width.

Fig. 7: Load/displacement plots for chevron-notched laminates tested in bending.

For the weakly-bonded laminates, prediction of the fracture energy is difficult, since the extent of debonding is unknown *a priori*. The effect of debonding is to introduce an initial crack opening displacement equal to the total debonded length. This will tend to reduce the magnitude of the peak load (maximum constraint factor), but increase the displacement at ligament rupture. A consequence of the general shape of the load-displacement plot (Figs. 4 and 6) is that the maximum constraint has relatively little influence on the work done, since the load subsequently falls rather sharply with increasing strain. The effect of an increased displacement at failure is therefore expected to be more significant, so that the net effect of weakening the interface is to raise the fracture energy. This is consistent with these observations.

It should, however, be noted that, when multiple cracking is occurring, a weak interface may lead to fewer cracks being generated per unit length of specimen. This means that a reduction

in fracture energy will be effected under many conditions by weakening the interface. It should also be noted that a weak interface may be undesirable for other purposes, such as under conditions where the laminate may fail in shear.

Fig. 8: Comparison between predicted and measured fracture energy of aluminium-alumina laminates. The experimental data were obtained by bending of chevron-notched specimens.

CONCLUSIONS

1. Bending and tensile loading experiments have been carried out on aluminium-alumina laminates in order to measure the fracture energy. This was done on chevron-notched specimens in which fracture took place by propagation of a single dominant crack..
2. Modelling work aimed at predicting the fracture energy of such laminates has been focused on the work done during deformation of metal ligaments which bridge cracks in adjacent ceramic layers. A modified form of the Bridgman equation has been developed to predict the load borne by the bridging ligament as it deforms, necks down and fails.
3. The proposed form of the Bridgman equation is thought to be applicable to metals which undergo extensive plastic deformation and tend to neck down progressively until the load-bearing section falls to zero. Tensile loading experiments on single aluminium layers, constrained by notched ceramic layers bonded on both sides, confirmed that the observed load-displacement behaviour was generally similar to that predicted using this equation. Broad agreement was only observed when account was taken of the work-hardening characteristics of the aluminium. Work hardening tends to raise the total work done by requiring a higher load for deformation to continue, provided it does not lead to premature rupture.
4. Use of the modified form of the Bridgman equation allowed the work done in deforming a single ligament to be evaluated as a function of layer thickness and metal work hardening characteristics. This in turn allowed prediction of the fracture energy of a laminate during single crack propagation, as a function of metal volume fraction, for a given ceramic layer thickness. Comparison between predictions obtained in this way and experimentally measured laminate fracture energies showed good agreement.

5. The characteristic form of the load-displacement curve for constrained single layers shows a fairly sharp peak at low displacement, followed by a rapid fall and then a more shallow gradient as the section necks down. The work done tends to be more sensitive to the factors affecting the displacement at failure than to those which control the magnitude of the initial peak load. Consistent with this were observations that specimens with reduced interfacial bond strengths exhibited slightly higher fracture energies than those with strong interfaces. This is attributed to the effect of debonding in allowing a larger deformation zone in each metal ligament and consequently greater crack opening displacement at failure.

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REFERENCES

1. H. C. Cao and A. G. Evans, On Crack Extension in Ductile/Brittle Laminates, *Acta Met. Mater.*, 39(12) (1991), pp. 2997-3005.
2. M. C. Shaw, D. B. Marshall, M. S. Dadkhah and A. G. Evans, Cracking and Damage Mechanisms in Ceramic/Metal Multilayers, *Acta Metall. Mater.*, 41 (1993), pp. 3311-3320.
3. Z. Chen and J. J. Mecholsky, Control of Strength and Toughness of Ceramic/Metal Laminates Using Interface Design, *J. Mat. Res. Soc.*, 8(9) (1993), pp. 2362-2369.
4. T. Ozturk, J. Mirmesdagh and T. Ediz, Strain Partitioning and Plastic Flow in Some Metal/Metal Laminates, *Materials Science and Engineering*, A175 (1994), pp. 125-129.
5. Q. Ma, M. C. Shaw, M. Y. He, B. J. Dalgleish, D. R. Clarke and A. G. Evans, Stress Redistribution in Ceramic/Metal Multilayers Containing Cracks, *Acta Metall. et Mater.*, 43(6) (1995), pp. 2137-2142.
6. S. K. Pateras, M. C. Shaw, W. J. Clegg, A. C. F. Cocks and T. W. Clyne, The Effect of Metal Layer Thickness on Energy Absorption during Fracture of Metal/Ceramic Laminates, in *Proc. 10th Int. Conf. Comp. Mat. (ICCM10)*, A. Poursartip and K. Street (Eds.), Vol. 1, Woodhead, (1995), pp. 731-737.
7. S. K. Pateras, S. J. Howard and T. W. Clyne, The Contribution of Bridging Ligament Rupture to Energy Absorption during Fracture of Metal-Ceramic Laminates, *Key Eng. Mats.*, 127-131 (1996), pp. 1127-1136.
8. M. C. Shaw, T. W. Clyne, A. C. F. Cocks, N. A. Fleck and S. K. Pateras, Cracking Patterns in Ceramic/Metal Laminates, *J. Mech. Phys. Solids.*, 44 (1996), pp. 801-814.
9. P. A. Mataga, Deformation of Crack-Bridging Ductile Reinforcements in Toughened Brittle Materials, *Acta Metall.*, 37(12) (1989), pp. 3349-3359.

10. M. F. Ashby, F. J. Blunt and M. Bannister, Flow Characteristics of Highly Constrained Metal Wires, *Acta Metall.*, 37 (1989), pp. 1847-1857.
11. M. Bannister and M. F. Ashby, The Deformation and Fracture of Constrained Metal Sheets, *Acta Metall. Mater.*, 39 (1991), pp. 2575-2582.
12. M. Bannister, H. R. Shercliffe, G. Bao, F. Zok and M. F. Ashby, Toughening in Brittle Systems by Ductile Bridging Ligaments, *Acta Metall. Mater.*, 40 (1992), pp. 1531-1537.
13. A. G. Evans and R. M. McMeeking, On The Toughening of Ceramics by Strong Reinforcements, *Acta metall.*, 34(12) (1986), pp. 2435-2441.
14. S. Pateras, M. C. Shaw, W. J. Clegg and T. W. Clyne, The Effect of Metal Layer Thickness on the Fracture of Metal/Ceramic Laminates in Bending, in *High Performance Materials in Engine Technology*, P. Vincenzini (Ed.), Techna Srl., (1995), pp. 445-453.
15. N. Levy, Small Scale Yielding near a Crack in Plane Strain: a Finite Element Analysis, *Int. J. Fract. Mechs.*, 7 (1971), pp. 143-156.
16. J. R. Rice, Limitations to the Small Scale Yielding Approximation for Crack Tip Plasticity, *Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids*, 22 (1974), pp. 17-26.
17. M. F. Kanninen and C. H. Popelar, *Advanced Fracture Mechanics*, First edn., Oxford University Press, (1985).
18. H. L. Ewalds and R. J. H. Wanhill, *Fracture Mechanics*, 4 edn., Arnold DUM, London, (1989).
19. R. Hill, *The Mathematical Theory of Plasticity*, Oxford University Press, London, (1950).
20. J. R. Rice and M. A. Johnson, The Role of Large Crack Tip Geometry Changes in Plane Strain Fracture, in *Inelastic Behaviour of Solids*, M. F. Kanninen, W. F. Adler, A. R. Rosenfield and R. I. Jaffee (Eds.), McGraw-Hill, N.Y., (1970), pp. 641-672.
21. A. G. Evans and R. M. Cannon, Toughening of Brittle Solids by Martensitic Transformations, *Acta. Met.*, 34 (1986), pp. 761-800.
22. P. W. Bridgman, *Large Plastic Flow and Fracture*, 1st edn., McGraw-Hill, (1952).
23. L. S. Sigl, P. A. Mataga, B. J. Dalgleish, R. M. McMeeking and A. G. Evans, On the toughness of brittle materials reinforced with a ductile phase, *Acta Met. et Mater.*, 36(4) (1988), pp. 945-953.
24. S. Pateras, *Energy Absorption in Metal/Ceramic Laminates*, University of Cambridge (1997).
25. G. E. Dieter, *Mechanical Metallurgy*, McGraw-Hill, New York, (1986).